

Test-retest reliability of the 1-minute-sit-to-stand test in people with schizophrenia

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Abstract – While physical activity is an interesting strategy to diminish risk factors in schizophrenia, few reliable tools to assess the effectiveness of interventions are available in this population. The aim of this study was to assess the test-retest reliability of the 1-minute-sit-to-stand test (1'STS) in schizophrenia. We also investigated minimal detectable changes (MDC), associations between clinical and anthropometric outcomes and 1'STS and compared participants' performances with reference and predictive values. Thirty-four people with schizophrenia (7 women; age: 29 (12) years) performed three 1'STS (T1, T2 and T3) at a 15-minute and 24 to 72-hour interval, with motivation, effort perception and heart rate assessments. Median scores were 28.0 repetitions (8.5) in T1, 30.0 (9.8) in T2 and 30.5 (5.0) in T3. There was no learning effect. Intraclass correlation coefficients were 0.88 [0.77; 0.94] for T1-T2 and 0.93 [0.86; 0.96] for T2-T3. Typical error expressed as coefficient of variation was 11.7% for T1-T2 and 8.7% for T2-T3. MDC₉₅ and MDC₉₀ were 24% and 20%, respectively. Best performance was 61.3% of predicted values and 91% of participants scored below the median reference value. 1'STS performance was positively correlated to perception of respiratory effort ($r=0.358$; $p=0.038$) and peak heart rate ($r=0.350$; $p=0.042$), and negatively correlated to weight ($r=-0.398$; $p=0.049$) and BMI ($r=-0.425$; $p=0.034$) when accounting for sex. The 1'STS is a reliable test to assess physical fitness in schizophrenia in rehabilitation settings.

Keywords : Severe mental illness, Clinimetric properties, Validity, Testing, Motivation

Résumé – Reproductibilité test-retest du test de lever de chaise d'une minutes chez des personnes souffrant de schizophrénie. Bien que l'activité physique soit une stratégie intéressante pour diminuer les facteurs de risque de schizophrénie, peu d'outils fiables permettant d'évaluer l'efficacité de programmes en activité physique sont disponibles dans cette population. Cette étude a évalué la reproductibilité test-retest du test de lever de chaise d'une minute (1'STS) dans la schizophrénie. La différence minimale détectable (MDC), les associations entre le 1'STS et des indicateurs cliniques ont été investiguées, et les performances comparées avec des valeurs de référence et prédictives. Trente-quatre volontaires souffrant de schizophrénie (7 femmes ; 29 (12) ans) ont réalisé trois 1'STS (T1, T2, T3) espacés de 15 min puis de 24 à 72 heures respectivement, en mesurant motivation, perception d'effort et fréquence cardiaque. La performance médiane atteignait 28.0 (8.5), 30.0 (9.8) et 30.5 (5.0) répétitions respectivement, sans effet d'apprentissage. Les coefficients de corrélation intraclass étaient de 0.88 [0.77 ; 0.94] (T1-T2), et 0.93 [0.86 ; 0.96] (T2-T3). L'erreur type comme coefficient de variation était de 11.7% (T1-T2) et 8.7% (T2-T3). Les MDC₉₅ et MDC₉₀ étaient de 24% et 20%. La meilleure performance des participants atteignait 61.3% des valeurs prédites, 91% avaient une performance inférieure aux valeurs de référence. Le 1'STS était corrélé positivement à la perception de l'effort ventilatoire ($r=0.358$; $p=0.038$) et la fréquence cardiaque pic ($r=0.350$; $p=0.042$), et négativement à la masse corporelle ($r=-0.398$; $p=0.049$) et l'IMC ($r=-0.425$; $p=0.034$). Ces résultats confirment la reproductibilité du 1'STS pour évaluer la condition physique dans la schizophrénie dans un contexte de réhabilitation psychosociale.

Mots clés : Maladies mentales sévères, Propriétés clinimétriques, Validité, Testing, Motivation

INTRODUCTION

Schizophrenia is a psychiatric disease affecting about one percent of the population worldwide (Tréhout & Dollfus, 2018). While antipsychotics are the main solution to treat positive symptoms of schizophrenia (Stepnicki et al., 2018), adverse effects can include sedation, fatigue, extrapyramidal syndromes. They can also induce metabolic alterations, increasing risks of diabetes mellitus, hyperglycaemia, hyperlipidaemia and weight gain (Singh et al., 2019). It is now well established that people with schizophrenia (PZ) are more sedentary and less physically active when compared to the general healthy population (Vancampfort, Firth, et al., 2017), which may exacerbate the aforementioned comorbidities and contribute to reduced physical fitness. For instance, Perez-Cruzado et al. (2017) found that people with severe mental illnesses practicing regular physical activity had better physical fitness levels than those who were inactive. Reduced physical fitness may reinforce deconditioning, leading patients into a downward spiral of physical deconditioning, affecting daily activities and quality of life (Heggelund et al., 2011).

In this context, adding physical activity to the care package of PZ is an interesting strategy to diminish risk factors and increase physical fitness and well-being, as the benefits of regular physical activity are supported by several original studies and meta-analyses (Curcic et al., 2017; Firth et al., 2015; Firth, Cotter, et al., 2017; Firth, Stubbs, et al., 2017; Stubbs et al., 2018). However, availability of reliable tools to individualize and assess objectively the effectiveness of interventions remains limited in PZ.

Vancampfort et al. assessed the test-retest reliability of the Eurofit test, a battery of seven tests assessing general physical health, in fifty PZ or people suffering from schizoaffective disorder (Vancampfort, Probst, Sweers, Maurissen, Knapen, Willems, et al., 2011). Others assessed the test-retest reliability of walking tests (ie. 2-min and 6-min walking test) (Bernard et al., 2014; Gomes et al., 2016; Vancampfort, Probst, Sweers, Maurissen, Knapen, & De Hert, 2011; Vancampfort et al., 2019) and submaximal cycling tests (Vancampfort et al., 2014). While they provide useful information on various components of physical fitness, they also show limitations, impeding their regular use in some clinical settings. The Eurofit test requires a lot of space and is time consuming, walking tests require a 30-meter-long quiet corridor, while tests involving specific ergometers (e.g. Astrand-Rhyming cycling test) may not be relevant to most activities of daily living.

The 1 min sit-to-stand test (1'STS) is a simple functional test that has gained in popularity over the last decade. The 1'STS evaluates the number of times an individual can stand up and sit down on a chair over a one-minute period. It offers numerous advantages : it is easy to standardize, and requires minimal time, equipment (i.e., a chair and a stopwatch) and space (Bohannon & Crouch, 2018). The 1'STS is often considered as a versatile, multipurpose integrated test, as supported by several studies in various health and clinical contexts showing good associations with both markers of aerobic (e.g. peak oxygen uptake) (Combret et al., 2021; Gruet et al., 2016; Reychler et al., 2019) and neuromuscular (e.g. quadriceps strength) (Gruet et al., 2016; Radtke et al., 2016; Reychler et al., 2020) fitness. Evaluating this latter is of particular relevance in PZ as they exhibit impaired muscle force-generating capacity which can be addressed through strength training (Nygård et al., 2019, 2021). Then, the 1'STS may be useful for assessing the effectiveness of programs targeting limb muscle function on a regular basis.

In addition, reference values are available for both healthy children (Haile et al., 2021) and adults, for which a predictive equation of performance has been established (Strassmann et al., 2013). Clinical utility of the 1'STS has been established in many populations through the confirmation of reliability, convergent validity or responsiveness to intervention (Bohannon & Crouch, 2018; Crook, Puhan, et al., 2017; Haile et al., 2021; Radtke et al., 2016; Segura-Ortí & Martínez-Olmos, 2011; Sevillano-Castaño et al., 2023; Strassmann et al., 2013). However, its test-retest reliability, an essential

prerequisite for being used as a screening test or to detect improvements from a given intervention, has never been evaluated in PZ. While this test has demonstrated excellent reliability, some studies found a learning effect in specific populations. Moreover, 1'STS reliability results from previous studies may not be extrapolated to PZ, as they exhibit motivation impairments (Lee et al., 2015). This is particularly relevant for the 1'STS, as its self-regulated pace may lead to performance variations due to changes in motivation, affecting test-retest reliability.

Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate both intra-day (i.e., 15 minutes) and inter-day (i.e., 24 to 72 hours) reliability of the 1'STS in PZ. Due to the short duration of the test, we hypothesized that despite small variations in motivation, the test-retest reliability of the test would be good.

Secondary objectives were to : (i) calculate the minimal detectable change (MDC), (ii) compare 1'STS performance with reference and predictive values and (iii) investigate the relationship between 1'STS performance and clinical and anthropometric outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Subjects

PZ were recruited amongst patients accompanied in their functional recovery process in a French psychosocial rehabilitation centre. Before enrolment, every participant was informed about potential risks and benefits of the study and gave informed written consent. For participants under protective measures, information about the study was sent to the curators and guardians. In addition, for those under guardianship, guardians were also asked for their informed written consent. This study adhered to the standards mentioned in the latest revision of the Declaration of Helsinki (except being registered in a database) and was approved by a national ethics committee (CERSTAPS; IRB00012476-2022-15-03-162).

Patients with DSM-V diagnosis of schizophrenia and a dimensional PANSS assessment, stable medication (no antipsychotic modification for at least 4 weeks before the test), an absence of depressive symptoms and being 18 years-old or older were included. Patients presenting pain (EVA>1), precedents of inflammatory pathology, severe brain trauma, chronic respiratory pathology, medical contraindication to the practice of moderate intensity PA and/or dependence to toxic products such as alcohol, cannabis, or other toxic substances other than tobacco were excluded in the study. Patients with electroconvulsive therapy treatment were also excluded.

Design of the study and sample size calculation

Study design was similar to the protocol used by Haile et al. (2021) to test 1'STS reliability in healthy children. Evaluations were conducted on two separate visits. The first one evaluated intra-day reliability : participants were asked to perform two 1'STS, with a 15-minute break between trials. The second visit occurred 24 to 72 hours after the first, where participants performed a third 1'STS to assess inter-day reliability. Participants were asked to restrain from engaging into intense and/or unusual physical effort between the two visits.

Sample size calculation was performed based on minimal acceptable and expected inter-day reliability. Minimal acceptable reliability (ρ_0) is usually “moderate reliability” (i.e. $ICC \geq 0.5$) and expected reliability (ρ_1) for 1'STS is usually “excellent reliability” (i.e. $ICC \geq 0.9$). For instance Radtke et al. (2016) found $ICC = 0.98$ (95% CI 0.96 to 0.99) in people with CF, whereas Souron et al. (2024) found $ICC = 0.93$ (95% CI 0.88–0.96) in young healthy adults. However, following our rationale, we expect a slightly lower reliability in PZ. Accordingly, with $\rho_0 \geq 0.6$, $\rho_1 \geq 0.85$, a power of 0.9 and an alpha error of 0.05 (two-tailed), a minimum of 35 participants was required.

Subjects' characteristics

Age, height, and weight were recorded for each patient, BMI was calculated. Patients were asked if they were smokers, and had to complete the Simple Physical Activity Questionnaire (Rosenbaum et al., 2020), to assess sedentary and active times of the past week.

Psychiatric diagnosis

French versions of the Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (Kay et al., 1987; Lançon et al., 1997) and the Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (Overall et al., 1967; Overall & Gorham, 1962) were used to assess severity of schizophrenia. The Functional Remission of Global Schizophrenia scale (Rouillon et al., 2012) and the Global assessment of Functioning (American Psychiatric Association, 1994) were used to express its functional impact.

1'STS procedure

All tests were conducted by the same experimenter, using a standard height chair (46cm) without armrests placed against a wall. Test procedure was similar to the recommended procedures (Bohannon & Crouch, 2018; Haile et al., 2021). To allow learning effect analysis, participants were naïve to the test prior to their first visit, and they did not undergo a familiarization session. Participants were however allowed a few sit-to-stand trials (3 to 5 sit-to stands) prior to each test, which allowed them to test the movement and adjust their position on the chair if necessary, and acted as a warmup.

Participants started the test sitting down on the chair with their feet flat on the floor and were instructed to repeatedly stand up and sit down on the chair as many times as possible during one minute. They were not allowed to use their arms and were asked to either cross their arms over their chest or put their hands on their hips. Participants were informed that rest was allowed if needed during the test, but were advised to resume as soon as they could as the purpose of the test was to complete as many sit-to-stands as possible. They were not encouraged, but were informed when 15 seconds remained, and were reminded to stand up fully if they failed to do so. A full sit-to-stand-to-sit, where the legs had to be fully extended in the standing position, and the buttocks had to touch the seating area of the chair in sitting position, counted as one repetition; only complete repetitions were counted.

Before each 1'STS, participants were asked to rate their motivation to complete the test on a visual analogue scale going from “*I am not motivated at all*” to “*I am highly motivated*”. Immediately at the end of the test, using a modified (0-10) Borg's scale (Borg, 1990), subjects rated their perception of muscular and respiratory efforts, going from 0 (anchor : “nothing at all”) to 10 (anchor : “extremely strong”). As perceptual responses to exercise can be regionalized during whole-body exercise (e.g. Bolgar et al., 2010; Gruet et al., 2018), we used differentiated perceived effort scores (Robertson & Noble, 1997), as usually recommended in 1'STS standard operating procedures (Saynor et al., 2023). Briefly, participants were asked to rate perceived muscular effort based on the difficulty to contract their leg muscles; and to rate perceived respiratory effort based on how heavily they were breathing. Heart rate and oxygen saturation were recorded immediately at the end of the test with a pulse oximeter (CMS50N, Contec Medical Systems, China). For each subject's best 1'STS performance, peak heart rate was expressed as a percentage of predicted maximal heart rate following Tanaka's equation (2001) : $208 - 0.7 \times \text{age}$.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive characteristics of subjects and test data were summarised as mean - standard deviation or median - interquartile range, minimal value, and maximal value. Normality for each variable was verified using Shapiro-Wilk's test.

Repeated-measure analysis of variance (ANOVA) were performed to detect potential learning effects between tests and assess eventual variations in motivation. We defined a learning effect as a

significant difference between the first and second test (T1<T2; intra-day) or the second and third test (T2<T3; inter-day). As conditions for the application for parametric ANOVA were not met, Friedman tests and Conover's post-hoc tests were used.

Test-retest reliability of sit-to-stand test performance, peak heart rate and effort perception was assessed by calculating the intra-class correlation coefficient two-way mixed effects consistency (ICC_{3.1}). The 95% confidence interval of ICC estimates were interpreted as follows: poor (< 0.5), moderate (0.50 – 0.74), good (0.75 – 0.89), and excellent (≥ 0.9) (Koo & Li, 2016). Absolute reliability was assessed using typical error (TE) expressed as a coefficient of variation (CV_{TE}). Separate analyses were performed between the first (T1) and second test (T2) for intra-day reliability, and between T2 and the last test (T3) for inter-day reliability. Global reliability including T1-T2-T3 was also calculated. Bland and Altman 95% limits of agreement were plotted to offer additional representations of measurement error for 1'STS performance (Bland & Altman, 1999).

Finally, we calculated minimal detectable change (MDC) with the following equation : $MDC_{95} = SEM \times \sqrt{2} \times 1.96$ (Beckerman et al., 2001; Stratford et al., 1996). MDC₉₅ is the smallest value in change that can be interpreted as a real change with a 95% degree of confidence. To allow comparisons with data found in the literature, we also calculated MDC₉₀, with $MDC_{90} = SEM \times \sqrt{2} \times 1.64$. SEM is the standard error of measurement and corresponds to the within-subject standard deviation (Bland & Altman, 1996; Hopkins, 2000).

For each participant, we used their best performance, sex and age to compare them to reference values (Strassmann et al., 2013). Predictive values were calculated with Strassman's equation using sex, age and tobacco consumption (Strassmann et al., 2013), and were compared to test performances using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests.

Correlations were calculated to investigate whether any subjects' clinical or anthropometric characteristics or test parameters were correlated to the 1'STS performance. Pearson's correlations were used for continuous variables if paired variables followed a bivariate normal distribution. Otherwise, Spearman rank correlations were used.

Descriptive statistics, correlations, MDC and reliability calculations as well as comparisons of means were done using Jasp (ver. 0.16.4.0) and Excel (ver. 16.87), figures were made using Prism (ver. 9.0.1) and Excel..

RESULTS

Participants

Thirty-nine patients were eligible and were asked to participate: 5 were not interested to partake in the study, and 34 patients were finally included. Subjects' main characteristics are available in Table 1, 20.6% (n = 7) of participants were female, and 79.4% (n=27) were smokers.

Table 1

Population Characteristics

Variable	mean \pm SD or median (IQR)	min	max
Age (years)	29 (12)	21	56
Height (m)	1.76 (0.1)	1.47	1.87
Weight (kg)	82.6 \pm 16.7	55.0	116.0
BMI (kg.m-2)	26.6 \pm 4.2	19.5	36.3

Sedentary time (h/day)	10.5 ± 2.0	4.0	16.0
Active time (h/day)	1.3 (2.1)	0.16	5.0
PANSS global score	58.6 ± 12.6	37.0	82.0
BPRS	40.9 ± 9.0	27.0	58.0
FROGS scale global score	64.5 ± 9.9	46.0	87.0
GAF	62.2 ± 12.3	38.0	85.0

Note. BMI = body mass index; BPRS = Brief Psychiatry Rating Scale; FROGS = Functional Remission of General Schizophrenia; GAF = Global Assessment of Functioning; IQR = interquartile range; PANSS = Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale; SD = standard deviation

Learning effect and reliability

All participants completed the 3 tests. No significant oxygen desaturation was observed during the tests. On average, peak heart rate at the end of the best test reached $70 \pm 10\%$ of theoretical maximal heart rate.

Boxplots of Fig.1 show median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of sit-to-stand performance (Fig.1.a) and of motivation to perform the tests (Fig.1.b) across trials. For 1'STS performance, while the repeated measure ANOVA was significant ($p=0.02$), post-hoc analysis revealed only a significant difference between T1 and T3 ($p=0.02$). No significant differences were detected between T1 and T2 ($p=0.95$), and T2 and T3 ($p=0.24$), indicating no learning effect. Motivation did not vary significantly between T1, T2 and T3 ($p=0.39$).

Figure 1

Boxplots of 1'STS performance and motivation across trials

Note. Fig.1.a Boxplots of 1'STS performance across trials, with median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of sit-to-stand performance across trials; 1.b Boxplots of motivation to perform the tests, with median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of motivation to perform the tests across trials

Intra-day and inter-day reliability are shown in Table 2 and Table 3, respectively. Global reliability, calculated across the three tests, is shown in Table 4. Boxplots of Fig.2 show median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of peak heart rate (Fig.2.a), muscular effort perception (Fig.2.b) and respiratory effort perception (Fig.2.c) across trials.

Figure 2

Boxplots of peak heart rate, muscular and respiratory effort perception across trials

Note. Fig.2.a Boxplots of peak heart rate across 1'STS trials, with median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of peak heart rate (bpm) across trials; 2.b Boxplots of muscular effort perception across trials, with median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of effort perception to perform the tests across trials; 2.c Boxplots of respiratory effort perception across trials, with median (25th, 75th percentiles), min and max of effort perception to perform the tests across trials; bpm = beats per minute

Table 2

Intra-day reliability (T1 vs. T2) of the 1'STS

	1'STS 1	1'STS 2	Change in mean [95% CI]	ICC ₃₋₁ [95% CI]	TE as CV (%) [95% CI]
Sit-to-stands (n)	28.0 (8.5)	30.0 (9.8)	1.5 [1.5 ; 1.6]	0.88 [0.77 ; 0.94]	11.7 [9.4 ; 15.4]
Peak HR (bpm)	125.8 (14.4)	132.0 (18.1)	6.2 [9.8 ; 2.6]	0.80 [0.64 ; 0.90]	5.6 [4.5 ; 7.4]
Muscular effort perception (Borg 0-10)	5.0 (4.0)	5.0 (3.8)	-0.06 [-0.08 ; -0.04]	0.79 [0.61 ; 0.89]	20.4 [16.5 ; 26.9]
Respiratory effort perception (Borg 0-10)	5.7 ± 2.2	5.8 ± 2.1	0.15 [0.13 ; 0.16]	0.76 [0.57 ; 0.87]	18.5 [15.0 ; 24.4]

Note. bpm = beats per minute; CI = confidence interval; HR = heart rate; ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient; SD = standard deviation; TE as CV = typical error expressed as coefficient of variation

Table 3

Inter-day reliability (T2 vs.T3) of the 1'STS

	1'STS 2	1'STS 3	Change in mean [95% CI]	ICC ₃₋₁ [95% CI]	TE as CV (%) [95% CI]
Sit-to-stands (n)	30.0 (9.8)	30.5 (5.0)	0.74 [0.69 ; 0.78]	0.93 [0.86 ; 0.96]	8.7 [7.0 ; 11.4]
Peak HR(bpm)	132.0 (18.1)	130.0 (16.8)	-2.0 [-5.4 ; 4.6]	0.67 [0.43 ; 0.82]	7.7 [6.2 ; 10.1]
Muscular effort perception (Borg 0-10)	5.0 (3.8)	5.4 ± 2.4	0.15 [0.13 ; 0.17]	0.67 [0.43 ; 0.82]	24.9 [20.1 ; 32.8]
Respiratory effort perception (Borg 0-10)	5.8 ± 2.1	5.7 ± 2.1	-0.12 [-0.10 ; -0.13]	0.76 [0.58 ; 0.87]	17.9 [14.4 ; 23.6]

Note. bpm = beats per minute; CI = confidence interval; HR = heart rate; ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient; SD = standard deviation; TE as CV = typical error expressed as coefficient of variation

Table 4

Global reliability (T1 vs. T2 vs. T3) of the 1'STS

	<i>mean ±SD or median (IQR)</i>	<i>ICC₃₋₁ [95% CI]</i>	<i>TE as CV (%) [95% CI]</i>
<i>Sit-to-stands (n)</i>	29 (8)	0.90 [0.83 ; 0.94]	10.2 [8.4 ; 13.3]
<i>Peak HR (bpm)</i>	129 (20.5)	0.69 [0.53 ; 0.82]	6.8 [5.6 ; 8.8]
<i>Muscular effort perception (Borg 0-10)</i>	5 (4)	0.73 [0.58 ; 0.84]	22.7 [18.7 ; 29.5]
<i>Respiratory effort perception (Borg 0-10)</i>	6 ± 2.1	0.72 [0.57 ; 0.84]	18.3 [15.1 ; 23.8]

Note. bpm = beats per minute; CI = confidence interval; HR = heart rate; ICC = intraclass correlation coefficient; IQR = interquartile range; SD = standard deviation; TE as CV = typical error expressed as coefficient of variation

Figure 3 shows Bland and Altman plots for 1'STS performance across trials. For each plot, the central line shows the mean difference between T1 and T2, and T2 and T3, respectively. Graphs show the absence of systematic bias, as the confidence intervals of the mean difference values include 0 (Bland & Altman, 1996; Giavarina, 2015).

Figure 3

Bland and Altman plot of 1'STS performance between trials

Note. 3.a Bland and Altman plot of 1'STS performance between T1 and T2; 2.b Bland and Altman plot of 1'STS performance between T2 and T3; for both graphs, the central dotted line corresponds to the mean difference (95%CI), the lower and higher continuous lines represent the limits of agreement (95%CI)

MDC₉₅ and MDC₉₀

Both MDC₉₅ and MDC₉₀ were calculated based on 1'STS performance scores of T2 and T3. MDC₉₅ and MDC₉₀ were respectively 7.6 and 6.4 sit-to-stands, corresponding to 24% and 20%, respectively, when expressing values as a percentage of the average test score.

Comparison with reference and predictive values

We compared participants' best 1'STS performance with reference values provided by Strassman and al. (2013), depending on their sex and age. For the majority of our sample (91%), the best performance was below the median score indicated in the reference values. Fig.4 shows the detailed repartition of participants' performance in regard to reference values.

Best performance was 33.6 ± 10.2 repetitions, corresponding to 61.3% of predicted values. Patients' performances were significantly lower than predicted scores ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 4

Pie chart of the repartition of 1'STS maximal performance relative to percentiles of reference values

Correlations of the 1'STS with participants' characteristics

Highest 1'STS performance was positively correlated with respiratory effort perception ($r=0.358$; $p=0.038$) and peak heart rate ($r=0.350$; $p=0.042$). When accounting for sex, highest test performance was negatively correlated with weight ($r=-0.398$; $p=0.049$) and BMI ($r=-0.425$; $p=0.034$). Performance was not correlated to any clinical characteristics such as functional impact of schizophrenia or PANSS scores.

DISCUSSION

In this study, we found good to excellent intra-day and inter-day test-retest reliability for the 1'STS as well as MDC₉₅ and MDC₉₀ of 24% and 20%, respectively. Compared to reference and predictive values, participants' best performances were 61.3% of predicted values, and most of our participants scored below the median reference score.

Learning effect and test-retest reliability

There is no consensus as how to define learning effect in sport sciences: some authors such as Vancampfort and al. (2011, 2014) define it as a combination of multiple factors, including ICC and Pearson correlations less than 0.75, a significant increase of performance between successive trials, and a Bland-Altman plot interpretation, whereas others consider it as a significant increase in test performance between two consecutive trials (Combret et al., 2021; Haile et al., 2021; Radtke et al., 2016; Reychler et al., 2019). We referred to this second definition which is mostly used in studies investigating the 1'STS. We observed a slight non-significant increase in 1'STS performance (+1.5 repetition) between T1 and T2, that lessened between T2 and T3 (+0.7 repetition). As such, we consider there is no learning effect for the 1'STS in PZ. As participants were naïve to the test in T1, the absence of a learning effect cannot be attributed to a familiarization that occurred before the trials. If we were to

consider T1 as a familiarization for T2, it can be concluded that adding a familiarization before testing does not significantly impact participants performance. Learning effect in 1'STS varies between populations but also between settings : in young adults there was no learning effect (Souron et al. (2024), but in healthy children, it went from +5% (Reychler et al., 2019) to +10% (Haile et al., 2021). Contrasting learning effects occur in people with cardiorespiratory disorders, going from no effect (Reychler et al., 2018), to a small effect (+5%) in people with COPD (Crook, Büsching, et al., 2017), to a greater effect in lung transplant recipients (+16%) (Tarrant et al., 2020) and in people with cystic fibrosis (+18%) (Radtke et al., 2016). Differences in learning effects might be linked to pacing strategies depending on the presence of symptoms, and might be higher in people exhibiting dyspnoea on exertion than in patients without cardiorespiratory complications. In our sample, perception of respiratory effort was moderate (≈ 5.7), and participants did not desaturate, which could explain this absence of a learning effect. Our data also indicates that the 1'STS could be assessed without the use of an oximeter with patients without known cardiorespiratory comorbidities.

Despite the absence of a learning effect, our data suggests that undergoing a first 1'STS to ensure optimal reliability might be preferable. 1'STS performance exhibited good to excellent reliability between T1 and T2, T2 and T3 and across the three tests. However, we observed a slight increase in reliability, shown by the decrease in CV_{TE} values, increase in ICC values and the narrowing of the limits of agreement and the shift of the mean difference line towards zero in the Bland and Altman plots. Overall, our ICC and CV_{TE} values are consistent with those found in other populations, with ICCs of 0.80 (95% CI 0.65 to 0.89) in adults (Ritchie et al., 2005), 0.90 (95% CI 0.83 to 0.95) in healthy children (Reychler et al., 2019), 0.91 (95% CI 0.76 to 0.96) in children with cystic fibrosis (Combret et al., 2021), 0.97 (95% CI 0.94 to 0.98) in adults undergoing haemodialysis (Segura-Ortí & Martínez-Olmos, 2011) and 0.98 (95% CI 0.96 to 0.99) in adults with cystic fibrosis (Radtke et al., 2016). This latter study also indicates a CV_{TE} of 3.8% in test performance, that reaches 12.8% in people with renal diseases (Koufaki et al., 2002).

In comparison to other populations, we expected small changes in motivation between tests, influencing 1'STS performance, as previous research reported motivation impairments in PZ (Lee et al., 2015). However, we did not find significant differences in motivation between trials, which might be explained by the length of the test (i.e. 1 min). Other tests requiring to sustain high effort levels for longer durations might be more prone to induce changes in motivation between trials, and affect test-retest reliability.

Whilst having a good to excellent reliability across all three trials and no learning effect, increases in reliability of ICCs and CV_{TE} for 1'STS performance suggests that at least one trial should be used to increase 1'STS' reliability, depending on the study's purpose. If the aim is to use the 1'STS as a diagnostic test for clinical purposes (e.g. an annual review assessment of physical functioning) or to compare performance to predictive or normal values, conducting only one 1'STS should be acceptable, especially considering reference values were derived from participants that performed the test only once. However, if the aim of a clinical research trial is to detect small differences pre-post interventions or between populations (e.g. comparing PZ with people with other mental disorders), it is advisable to perform the test twice.

To our knowledge, only Souron et al. (2024) investigated test-retest reliability of heart rate response and effort perception for the 1'STS. These are frequently assessed in clinical settings, as they convey additional information about one's psychological implication (i.e. effort perception) and the physiological demands (i.e. heart rate) of the 1'STS. They offer a broader perspective to interpret participant's performance and the effect of interventions. ICC values for peak heart rate were moderate to excellent between T1 and T2, and poor to good between T2 and T3. CV_{TE} went from 5.63 to 7.68% for T1-T2 and T2-T3, respectively. Overall reliability was moderate to good for this parameter. ICCs of

muscular effort perception were moderate to good between T1 and T2; and low to good between T2 and T3. For respiratory effort perception, ICCs were moderate to good for T1-T2 and T2-T3. For both parameters, overall reliability was moderate to good, and CV_{TE} were rather high as they ranged from 18 to 25%. This relatively high variability in effort perception could be explained by the presence of interoception abnormalities in PZ, making the interpretation of bodily signals more difficult and/or inaccurate in this population (Torregrossa et al., 2022; Yao & Thakkar, 2022). As such, the interpretation of these variables should be made with caution, especially when looking at their evolution across tests, for instance over the course of a rehabilitation protocol.

Minimal detectable change

MDC is the smallest change necessary to consider the observed change is not due to chance, with a certain degree of confidence. This indicator is particularly interesting in a rehabilitation context where tests are meant to be repeated over time, to make sure observed changes are real. In our case, a 24% increase in performance should be observed to confirm that observed improvements are real according to MDC_{95} . To our knowledge, only a few studies assessed MDC for this test: Sevillano-Castaño and al. (2023) found a MDC_{95} of 12% in long covid patients, and Segura-Ortí and Martínez-Olmos (2011) reported a MDC_{90} of 4 sit-to-stands in people with haemodialysis. Studies investigating other tests calculated relative MDCs, allowing comparison. In spinal cord injuries, MDC_{95} was 39% for the 10-meter walk test, 30% for the timed up and go test and 22% for the 6-min walk test (Lam et al., 2008). In schizophrenia, authors found a MDC_{95} of 19% for the Astrand-Rhyming test (Vancampfort et al., 2014), and in chronic stroke, they found a MDC_{95} of 13% for the 6-min walk test (Flansbjer et al., 2005). Considering previous studies evaluating the reliability of the 1'STS or other physical tests, our MDCs are within an acceptable range, and may serve as reference point when interpreting 1'STS performance changes following a given intervention.

Comparison with predictive values

Patients' performances only reached 61.3% of predicted values, which is consistent with previous studies showing reduced cardiorespiratory fitness (-8.96 mL/kg/min) (Vancampfort, Rosenbaum, et al., 2017), impaired force-generating capacity (-19%) and lower scores at the 6MWT (-22%) and stair climbing (-63%) (Nygård et al., 2019) in PZ compared to healthy controls.

This low performance can be explained by several factors. Predictive equation considered sex, age, and tobacco consumption of participants, but not weight or BMI. However, performance at the test was negatively correlated to BMI and weight when accounting for sex. The 1'STS requires participants to maintain balance and it has been shown that an increase in BMI is linked to higher postural sway in adults (Yadav et al., 2022). Our participants had an average BMI of 26.6 kg.m², and overweight and obesity can be considered as a secondary manifestation of schizophrenia as they are highly prevalent in this population (Afzal et al., 2021). PZ might experience more difficulties keeping their balance during the test, resulting in lower performances. Muscular dysfunction could be another reason for this low performance. The 1'STS is indeed an indicator of both muscle strength (Gruet et al., 2016; Radtke et al., 2016; Reychler et al., 2020) and muscle endurance (Souron et al., 2024) and PZ show impaired muscle force-generating capacity (Nygård et al., 2019). Patients showed high levels of sedentary behaviour, with on average 10.5h of sedentary time per day, which is higher than the general French population (6.6h in French adults in 2015) (Santé Publique France, 2017). As overall sedentary time is negatively correlated with cardiorespiratory fitness, muscle strength and balance in adults (Silva et al., 2020), three important components for the 1'STS, high levels of sedentary time in our population could also contribute to low 1'STS performance. Overall, the 1'STS could be a useful preliminary tool to identify low functional performance, and further research on its underlying physical factors using complementary tests (e.g. lower-limb strength assessment) seems necessary.

Poor 1'STS performance might also be explained by psychological factors. This test is self-regulated, and therefore highly motivation-dependant. Even if motivation scores did not vary significantly across trials, it is possible that motivation to perform the test was lower in PZ than in the general population, resulting in a lower investment during the test. To our knowledge, no other study investigated motivation to perform the 1'STS. We found that respiratory effort perception and peak heart rate, that may partially reflect engagement in such self-paced test, were positively correlated to 1'STS performance. However, since PZ show interoception abnormalities (Torregrossa et al., 2022; Yao & Thakkar, 2022), comparison of effort perception with healthy populations as an indicator of investment in a task might not be appropriate. Still, Souron et al. (2024) found that peak heart rate during the 1STS was $87 \pm 8\%$ of theoretical maximal heart rate, while it only reached $70 \pm 10\%$ in our sample of PZ, potentially indicating lower investment in the task, thus lower performances at the test. However, low peak heart rates could also be the consequence of chronotropic incompetence, previously reported in some people with schizophrenia (Herbsleb et al., 2018). Finally, self-stigma and self-efficacy could also have impacted participants performance. Internalization of stigma and prejudice is frequent in severe mental illnesses, and particularly in schizophrenia, as 42% of PZ experience self-stigma in Europe (Brohan et al., 2010), which is known to influence negatively levels of self-efficacy (Corrigan & Rao, 2012) and in turn impact physical performances (Harrison, 2004; Horcajo et al., 2022; Moritz et al., 2000; Wells et al., 1993). Self-stigma and low self-esteem in PZ might thus influence their physical performances in comparison to the general population.

In conclusion, reduced 1'STS performance in PZ can be explained by several manifestations of schizophrenia, making it an interesting test that might be sensitive to different interventions.

Limits

Our study has several limitations. First, as only one rater participated in the study, our study did not assess inter-rater reliability. However, the 1'STS is a very simple test to set up, scoring leaves little to interpretation and inter-rater reliability mainly depends on raters, not populations. Other studies found excellent inter-rater reliability ($ICC > 0.9$) (Tsekoura et al., 2020) and we expect similar findings in schizophrenia. More importantly, this research is a monocentric study, and our results might not be generalizable to all PZ. Our participants were PZ engaged in a psychosocial rehabilitation process with a stable medication, no depressive symptoms and no substance addiction other than tobacco. Results might not be applicable to other settings, such as PZ undergoing an acute episode, showing signs of depression or addiction. Further studies should confirm the excellent reliability of the 1'STS in other settings.

Practical implications

In summary, the 1'STS can be used in PZ as preliminary tool to detect disrupted functional performance in the lower limb. While our data shows a slight increase in reliability after a first 1'STS, there was no significant increase in performance, indicating no learning effect for the 1'STS in PZ. As such, in contexts where time is a limited resource, such as clinical settings, a familiarization session before testing is not necessary. However, if one's purpose is to detect very small changes in performance in a research context, we advise to do a trial session 15 minutes before testing. Furthermore, in participants without known cardiorespiratory comorbidities, the 1'STS can be assessed without monitoring oxygen saturation. Finally, our MDCs may be used as reference point to interpret changes in 1'STS performance after a given intervention: according to MDC_{95} , participants should improve their performance by 24% to confirm that their improvements are real.

Conclusion

This study showed that the 1'STS has a good to excellent test retest reliability in PZ, with an absence of

variations in motivation to perform the test, and no learning effect between trials. The 1'STS could be used in clinical settings as a simple, feasible test assessing patient's physical abilities. PZ exhibited lower 1'STS performance compared to reference values, suggesting the pertinence of this test to detect reduced physical fitness in this population. Users of the 1'STS should be aware that even in the absence of a learning effect, reliability of the test slightly improves with trial repetition. It might be advisable to undergo a first trial prior to evaluation for people naive to this test, especially in research studies aiming to detect small changes in performance.

REFERENCES

- Afzal, M., Siddiqi, N., Ahmad, B., Afsheen, N., Aslam, F., Ali, A., Ayesha, R., Bryant, M., Holt, R., Khalid, H., Ishaq, K., Koly, K. N., Rajan, S., Saba, J., Tirbhowan, N., & Zavala, G. A. (2021). Prevalence of Overweight and Obesity in People With Severe Mental Illness : Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Frontiers in Endocrinology*, *12*, 769309. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fendo.2021.769309>
- American Psychiatric Association. (1994). *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (4th ed.)* (4th edition). American Psychiatry Publishing, Inc.
- Beckerman, H., Roebroek, M. E., Lankhorst, G. J., Becher, J. G., Bezemer, P. D., & Verbeek, A. L. (2001). Smallest real difference, a link between reproducibility and responsiveness. *Quality of Life Research: An International Journal of Quality of Life Aspects of Treatment, Care and Rehabilitation*, *10*(7), 571-578. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1013138911638>
- Bernard, Romain, Vancampfort, Baillot, Esseul, & Ninot. (2014). Six-minute walk test for individuals with schizophrenia. *Disability and Rehabilitation*, *37*(11), 921-927. <https://doi.org/10.3109/09638288.2014.948136>
- Bland, J. M., & Altman, D. G. (1996). Statistics Notes : Measurement error. *BMJ (Clinical Research Ed.)*, *313*, 744. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.313.7059.744>
- Bland, J. M., & Altman, D. G. (1999). Measuring agreement in method comparison studies. *Statistical Methods in Medical Research*, *8*(2), 135-160. <https://doi.org/10.1177/096228029900800204>
- Bohannon, & Crouch. (2018). 1-Minute Sit-to-Stand Test : Systematic review of procedures, performance and clinimetric properties. *Journal of Cardiopulmonary Rehabilitation and Prevention*, *39*(1), 2-8. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HCR.0000000000000336>
- Bolgar, M. R., Baker, C. E., Goss, Fredric. L., Nagle, E., & Robertson, R. J. (2010). Effect of Exercise Intensity on Differentiated and Undifferentiated Ratings of Perceived Exertion During Cycle and Treadmill Exercise in Recreationally Active and Trained Women. *Journal of Sports Science & Medicine*, *9*(4), 557-563.
- Borg. (1990). Psychophysical scaling with applications in physical work and the perception of exertion. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, *16*(1), 55-58. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.1815>
- Brohan, E., Elgie, R., Sartorius, N., Thornicroft, G., & GAMIAN-Europe Study Group. (2010). Self-stigma, empowerment and perceived discrimination among people with schizophrenia in 14 European countries : The GAMIAN-Europe study. *Schizophrenia Research*, *122*(1-3), 232-238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2010.02.1065><https://doi.org/>
- Combret, Boujibar, Gennari, Medrinal, Sicinski, Bonnevie, Gravier, Laurans, Marguet, Le Roux, Lamia, Prieur, & Reychler. (2021). Measurement properties of the one-minute sit-to-stand test in children and adolescents with cystic fibrosis : A multicenter randomized cross-over trial. *PloS One*, *16*(2), e0246781. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0246781>
- Corrigan, P. W., & Rao, D. (2012). On the Self-Stigma of Mental Illness : Stages, Disclosure, and Strategies for Change. *Canadian journal of psychiatry. Revue canadienne de psychiatrie*, *57*(8), 464-469. <https://doi.org/10.1177/070674371205700804>
- Crook, Puhon, Frei, & STAND-UP and RIMTCORE study groups. (2017). The validation of the sit-to-stand test for COPD patients. *The European Respiratory Journal*, *50*(3), 1701506. <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.01506-2017>
- Crook, S., Büsching, G., Schultz, K., Leibert, N., Jelusic, D., Keusch, S., Wittmann, M., Schuler, M., Radtke, T., Frey, M., Turk, A., Puhon, M. A., & Frei, A. (2017). A multicentre validation of the 1-min sit-to-

- stand test in patients with COPD. *The European Respiratory Journal*, 49(3), 1601871. <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.01871-2016>
- Curcic, D., Stojmenovic, T., Djukic-Dejanovic, S., Dikic, N., Vesic-Vukasinovic, M., Radivojevic, N., Andjelkovic, M., Borovcanin, M., & Djokic, G. (2017). Positive impact of prescribed physical activity on symptoms of schizophrenia: Randomized clinical trial. *Psychiatria Danubina*, 29(4), 459-465. <https://doi.org/10.24869/psyd.2017.459>
- Firth, Cotter, Elliott, French, & Yung. (2015). A systematic review and meta-analysis of exercise interventions in schizophrenia patients. *Psychological Medicine*, 45(7), 1343-1361. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0033291714003110>
- Firth, J., Cotter, J., Carney, R., & Yung, A. R. (2017). The pro-cognitive mechanisms of physical exercise in people with schizophrenia. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 174(19), 3161-3172. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bph.13772>
- Firth, J., Stubbs, B., Rosenbaum, S., Vancampfort, D., Malchow, B., Schuch, F., Elliott, R., Nuechterlein, K. H., & Yung, A. R. (2017). Aerobic Exercise Improves Cognitive Functioning in People With Schizophrenia: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 43(3), 546-556. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/sbw115>
- Flansbjer, U.-B., Holmbäck, A. M., Downham, D., Patten, C., & Lexell, J. (2005). Reliability of gait performance tests in men and women with hemiparesis after stroke. *Journal of Rehabilitation Medicine*, 37(2), 75-82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/16501970410017215>
- Giavarina, D. (2015). Understanding Bland Altman analysis. *Biochemia Medica*, 25(2), 141-151. <https://doi.org/10.11613/BM.2015.015>
- Gomes, E., Bastos, T., Probst, M., Ribeiro, J. C., Silva, G., & Corredeira, R. (2016). Reliability and validity of 6MWT for outpatients with schizophrenia: A preliminary study. *Psychiatry Research*, 237, 37-42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2016.01.066>
- Gruet, M., Mely, L., & Vallier, J.-M. (2018). Overall and differentiated sensory responses to cardiopulmonary exercise test in patients with cystic fibrosis: Kinetics and ability to predict peak oxygen uptake. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 118(9), 2007-2019. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-018-3923-y>
- Gruet, Peyré-Tartaruga, Mely, & Vallier. (2016). The 1-Minute Sit-to-Stand Test in Adults With Cystic Fibrosis: Correlations With Cardiopulmonary Exercise Test, 6-Minute Walk Test, and Quadriceps Strength. *Respiratory Care*, 61(12), 1620-1628. <https://doi.org/10.4187/respcare.04821>
- Haile, Fühner, Granacher, Stocker, Radtke, & Kriemler. (2021). Reference values and validation of the 1-minute sit-to-stand test in healthy 5-16-year-old youth: A cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*, 11(5), e049143. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-049143><https://doi.org/>
- Harrison, A. L. (2004). The Influence of Pathology, Pain, Balance, and Self-efficacy on Function in Women With Osteoarthritis of the Knee. *Physical Therapy*, 84(9), 822-831. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/84.9.822>
- Heggelund, J., Hoff, J., Helgerud, J., Nilsberg, G. E., & Morken, G. (2011). Reduced peak oxygen uptake and implications for cardiovascular health and quality of life in patients with schizophrenia. *BMC Psychiatry*, 11(1), 188. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-244X-11-188>
- Herbsleb, M., Schumann, A., Malchow, B., Puta, C., Schulze, P. C., Gabriel, H. W., & Bär, K.-J. (2018). Chronotropic incompetence of the heart is associated with exercise intolerance in patients with schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Research*, 197, 162-169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2018.02.020>
- Hopkins, W. G. (2000). Measures of Reliability in Sports Medicine and Science: *Sports Medicine*, 30(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.2165/00007256-200030010-00001>
- Horcajo, J., Santos, D., & Higuero, G. (2022). The effects of self-efficacy on physical and cognitive performance: An analysis of meta-certainty. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 58, 102063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychsport.2021.102063>
- Kay, Fiszbein, & Opler. (1987). The Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS) for Schizophrenia. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*, 13(2), 261-276. <https://doi.org/10.1093/schbul/13.2.261>
- Koo, & Li. (2016). A Guideline of Selecting and Reporting Intraclass Correlation Coefficients for Reliability Research. *Journal of Chiropractic Medicine*, 15(2), 155-163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcm.2016.02.012>
- Koufaki, P., Mercer, T. H., & Naish, P. F. (2002). Effects of exercise training on aerobic and functional capacity of end-stage renal disease patients. *Clinical Physiology and Functional Imaging*, 22(2), 115-124. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2281.2002.00405.x>

- Lam, T., Noonan, V. K., & Eng, J. J. (2008). A systematic review of functional ambulation outcome measures in spinal cord injury. *Spinal cord*, 46(4), 246-254. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.sc.3102134>
- Lançon, Auquier, Llorca, Martinez, Bougerol, & Scotto. (1997). Etude des propriétés psychométriques de la PANSS dans sa version française dans une population de patients schizophrènes. *L'Encéphale*, 23(1), 1-9.
- Lee, Jung, Park, & Kim. (2015). Neural Basis of Anhedonia and Amotivation in Patients with Schizophrenia : The role of Reward System. *Current Neuropharmacology*, 13(6), 750-759. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1570159X13666150612230333>
- Moritz, S. E., Feltz, D. L., Fahrback, K. R., & Mack, D. E. (2000). The Relation of Self-Efficacy Measures to Sport Performance : A Meta-Analytic Review. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 71(3), 280-294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2000.10608908>
- Nygård, M., Brobakken, M. F., Roel, R. B., Taylor, J. L., Reitan, S. K., Güzey, I. C., Morken, G., Vedul-Kjelsås, E., Wang, E., & Heggelund, J. (2019). Patients with schizophrenia have impaired muscle force-generating capacity and functional performance. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 29(12), 1968-1979. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13526>
- Nygård, M., Brobakken, M. F., Taylor, J. L., Reitan, S. K., Güzey, I. C., Morken, G., Lydersen, S., Vedul-Kjelsås, E., Wang, E., & Heggelund, J. (2021). Strength training restores force-generating capacity in patients with schizophrenia. *Scandinavian Journal of Medicine & Science in Sports*, 31(3), 665-678. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13863>
- Overall, Hollister, & Pichot. (1967). Major Psychiatric Disorders : A Four-Dimensional Model. *Archives of General Psychiatry*, 16(2), 146. <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.1967.01730200014003>
- Overall, J. E., & Gorham, D. R. (1962). The brief psychiatric rating scale. *Psychological reports*, 10(3), 799-812. <https://doi.org/10.2466/pr0.1962.10.3.79>
- Radtke, Puhan, Hebestreit, & Kriemler. (2016). The 1-min sit-to-stand test—A simple functional capacity test in cystic fibrosis? *Journal of Cystic Fibrosis: Official Journal of the European Cystic Fibrosis Society*, 15(2), 223-226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcf.2015.08.006>
- Reychler, Audag, Mestre, & Caty. (2019). Assessment of Validity and Reliability of the 1-Minute Sit-to-Stand Test to Measure the Heart Rate Response to Exercise in Healthy Children. *JAMA Pediatrics*, 173(7), 692-693. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2019.1084>
- Reychler, G., Boucard, E., Peran, L., Pichon, R., Le Ber-Moy, C., Ouksel, H., Liistro, G., Chambellan, A., & Beaumont, M. (2018). One minute sit-to-stand test is an alternative to 6MWT to measure functional exercise performance in COPD patients. *The Clinical Respiratory Journal*, 12(3), 1247-1256. <https://doi.org/10.1111/crj.12658>
- Reychler, Pincin, Audag, Poncin, & Caty. (2020). One-minute sit-to-stand test as an alternative tool to assess the quadriceps muscle strength in children. *Respiratory Medicine and Research*, 78, 100777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmer.2020.100777>
- Ritchie, Trost, Brown, & Armit. (2005). Reliability and validity of physical fitness field tests for adults aged 55 to 70 years. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 8(1), 61-70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1440-2440\(05\)80025-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1440-2440(05)80025-8)
- Robertson, R. J., & Noble, B. J. (1997). Perception of physical exertion : Methods, mediators, and applications. *Exercise and Sport Sciences Reviews*, 25, 407-452.
- Rosenbaum, Morell, Abdel-Baki, Ahmadpanah, Anilkumar, Baie, Bauman, Bender, Boyan Han, Brand, Bratland-Sanda, Bueno-Antequera, Camaz Deslandes, Carneiro, Carraro, Castañeda, Castro Monteiro, Chapman, Chau, ... Ward. (2020). Assessing physical activity in people with mental illness : 23-country reliability and validity of the simple physical activity questionnaire (SIMPAQ). *BMC Psychiatry*, 20(1), 108. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12888-020-2473-0>
- Rouillon, Baylé, Gorwood, Lancrenon, Lançon, & Llorca. (2012). Évaluation de la rémission fonctionnelle dans le trouble schizophrénique : L'échelle FROGS. *L'Encéphale*, 39(Supplément 1), S15-S21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.encep.2012.09.002>
- Santé Publique France. (2017, septembre). *Étude de santé sur l'environnement, la biosurveillance, l'activité physique et la nutrition (Esteban) 2014-2016. Volet nutrition. Chapitre Activité physique et sédentarité.*
- Saynor, Z. L., Gruet, M., McNarry, M. A., Button, B., Morrison, L., Wagner, M., Sawyer, A., Hebestreit, H., Radtke, T., Urquhart, D. S., & European Cystic Fibrosis Society Exercise Working Group. (2023). Guidance and standard operating procedures for functional exercise testing in cystic fibrosis. *European*

- Respiratory Review: An Official Journal of the European Respiratory Society*, 32(169), 230029. <https://doi.org/10.1183/16000617.0029-2023>
- Segura-Ortí, & Martínez-Olmos. (2011). Test-retest reliability and minimal detectable change scores for sit-to-stand-to-sit tests, the six-minute walk test, the one-leg heel-rise test, and handgrip strength in people undergoing hemodialysis. *Physical Therapy*, 91(8), 1244-1252. <https://doi.org/10.2522/ptj.20100141>
- Sevillano-Castaño, A. I., Peroy-Badal, R., Torres-Castro, R., Cañuelo-Márquez, A. M., Rozalén-Bustín, M., Modrego-Navarro, Á., De Sousa-De Sousa, L., Ramos-Álvarez, J. J., Maté-Muñoz, J. L., & García-Fernández, P. (2023). Test-Retest Reliability and Minimal Detectable Change in Chester Step Test and 1-Minute Sit-to-Stand Test in Long COVID Patients. *Applied Sciences*, 13(14), Article 14. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13148464>
- Silva, F. M., Duarte-Mendes, P., Rusenhack, M. C., Furmann, M., Nobre, P. R., Fachada, M. Â., Soares, C. M., Teixeira, A., & Ferreira, J. P. (2020). Objectively Measured Sedentary Behavior and Physical Fitness in Adults : A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(22), 8660. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17228660>
- Singh, Bansal, Medhi, & Kuhad. (2019). Antipsychotics-induced metabolic alterations : Recounting the mechanistic insights, therapeutic targets and pharmacological alternatives. *European Journal of Pharmacology*, 844, 231-240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2018.12.003>
- Souron, R., Ruiz-Cárdenas, J. D., & Gruet, M. (2024). The 1-min sit-to-stand test induces a significant and reliable level of neuromuscular fatigability : Insights from a mobile app analysis. *European Journal of Applied Physiology*, 124, 3291-3301. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-024-05537-9>
- Stepnicki, P., Kondej, M., & Kaczor, A. A. (2018). Current Concepts and Treatments of Schizophrenia. *Molecules*, 23(8), Article 8. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules23082087>
- Strassmann, Steurer-Stey, Lana, Zoller, Turk, Suter, & Puhan. (2013). Population-based reference values for the 1-min sit-to-stand test. *International Journal of Public Health*, 58(6), 949-953. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-013-0504-z>
- Stratford, P. W., Binkley, J., Solomon, P., Finch, E., Gill, C., & Moreland, J. (1996). Defining the Minimum Level of Detectable Change for the Roland-Morris Questionnaire. *Physical Therapy*, 76(4), 359-365. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/76.4.359>
- Stubbs, B., Vancampfort, D., Hallgren, M., Firth, J., Veronese, N., Solmi, M., Brand, S., Cordes, J., Malchow, B., Gerber, M., Schmitt, A., Correll, C. U., De Hert, M., Gaughran, F., Schneider, F., Kinnafick, F., Falkai, P., Möller, H.-J., & Kahl, K. G. (2018). EPA guidance on physical activity as a treatment for severe mental illness : A meta-review of the evidence and Position Statement from the European Psychiatric Association (EPA), supported by the International Organization of Physical Therapists in Mental Health (IOPTMH). *European Psychiatry: The Journal of the Association of European Psychiatrists*, 54, 124-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2018.07.004>
- Tanaka, H., Monahan, K. D., & Seals, D. R. (2001). Age-predicted maximal heart rate revisited. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 37(1), 153-156. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0735-1097\(00\)01054-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0735-1097(00)01054-8)
- Tarrant, B. J., Robinson, R., Le Maitre, C., Poulsen, M., Corbett, M., Snell, G., Thompson, B. R., Button, B. M., & Holland, A. E. (2020). The Utility of the Sit-to-Stand Test for Inpatients in the Acute Hospital Setting After Lung Transplantation. *Physical Therapy*, 100(7), 1217-1228. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ptj/pzaa057>
- Torregrossa, L. J., Amedy, A., Roig, J., Prada, A., & Park, S. (2022). Interoceptive functioning in schizophrenia and schizotypy. *Schizophrenia research*, 239, 151-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.schres.2021.11.046>
- Tréhout, & Dollfus. (2018). L'activité physique chez les patients atteints de schizophrénie : De la neurobiologie aux bénéfices cliniques. *L'Encéphale*, 44(6), 538-547. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.encep.2018.05.005>
- Tsekoura, M., Anastasopoulos, K., Kastrinis, A., & Dimitriadis, Z. (2020). What is most appropriate number of repetitions of the sit-to-stand test in older adults : A reliability study. *Journal of Frailty, Sarcopenia and Falls*, 5(4), 109-113. <https://doi.org/10.22540/JFSF-05-109>
- Vancampfort, D., Kimbowa, S., Basangwa, D., Smith, L., Stubbs, B., Van Damme, T., De Hert, M., & Mugisha, J. (2019). Test-retest reliability, concurrent validity and correlates of the two-minute walk test in outpatients with psychosis. *Psychiatry Research*, 282, 112619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2019.112619>
- Vancampfort, D., Rosenbaum, S., Schuch, F., Ward, P. B., Richards, J., Mugisha, J., Probst, M., & Stubbs, B. (2017). Cardiorespiratory Fitness in Severe Mental Illness : A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Sports Medicine*, 47(2), 343-352. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-016-0574-1>

- Vancampfort, Firth, Schuch, Rosenbaum, Mugisha, Hallgren, Probst, Ward, Gaughran, & De Hert. (2017). Sedentary behavior and physical activity levels in people with schizophrenia, bipolar disorder and major depressive disorder : A global systematic review and meta-analysis. *World Psychiatry, 16*(3), 308-315. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20458>
- Vancampfort, Guelinckx, De Hert, Stubbs, Soundy, Rosenbaum, De Schepper, & Probst. (2014). Reliability and clinical correlates of the Astrand–Rhyming sub-maximal exercise test in patients with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder. *Psychiatry Research, 220*(3), 778-783. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2014.08.049>
- Vancampfort, Probst, Sweers, Maurissen, Knapen, & De Hert. (2011). Reliability, minimal detectable changes, practice effects and correlates of the 6-min walk test in patients with schizophrenia. *Psychiatry Research, 187*(1-2), 62-67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2010.11.027>
- Vancampfort, Probst, Sweers, Maurissen, Knapen, Willems, Heip, & De Hert. (2011). Eurofit test battery in patients with schizophrenia or schizoaffective disorder : Reliability and clinical correlates. *European Psychiatry, 27*(6), 416-421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2011.01.009>
- Wells, C. M., Collins, D., & Hale, B. D. (1993). The self-efficacy-performance link in maximum strength performance. *Journal of Sports Sciences, 11*(2), 167-175. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640419308729980>
- Yadav, A., Yadav, M., Verma, R., Kumari, M., & Arora, S. (2022). Effect of obesity on balance : A literature review. *International Journal of Health Sciences, 6*(S4), 3261-3279. <https://doi.org/10.53730/ijhs.v6nS4.9126>
- Yao, B., & Thakkar, K. (2022). Interoception abnormalities in schizophrenia : A review of preliminary evidence and an integration with Bayesian accounts of psychosis. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews, 132*, 757-773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2021.11.016>